

**MOTIVATIONAL INCENTIVES AND THE PERFORMANCE OF ELECTRICITY
SERVICES IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.**

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Abstract: The study evaluated motivational incentives and the Performance of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria. The Specific Objectives: examine the relationship between recognition and rewards on the output and evaluate the relationship between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 470 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 211, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error was used. 194 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings include that there was positive relationship between recognition and rewards on the output ($r = .392 < .794, p < .05$). There was positive linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria, ($r = .425 < .700$). The study concluded that recognition and rewards, professional development had positive significant relationship with the output and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study recommended amongst others that the management should endeavour to recognise hard work and reward the employees to motivate the staff, which will boost teamwork and productivity. It will improve the workplace culture and creating a supportive work environment.

Keywords: Motivation, Incentives, Performance, Services, Recognition, Rewards, Output

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Crucial to the success of an organization is competence of the management and workforce, employees' productivity on the other hand, had been hinged on the employee's capability and motivation received amongst

other factors, to perform the various tasks assigned to the employee. Many businesses incorrectly focus on what employees can do for them, instead of wondering what they can do to make sure each team member feels valued. A business cannot retain a motivated employee if they do not reward employee hard work and productivity (Morrow, 2020). The assumptions of scientific management were that work is inherently unpleasant for most people and the money they earn is more important than the nature of the job they are performing. Understanding motivation gives many valuable insights into human nature. Positive expectations of success enhance an employee's motivation. The level of motivation received by an employee as reflected in the satisfaction with the base pay package and other incentives goes a long way to influencing the employees' attitude to work, loyalty, performance and job satisfaction (Oloke, Oni, Babalola & Ojelabi, 2017). Motivation does not only encourage productive performance but also show employees how much the organization cares and values their presence and input. One of the most important goals of every organisation is to have employees who are highly performing and are motivated to work at all time. Achieving this dream has been cumbersome because of dynamic and complex behaviour of workers. The organization's reward system is the basic structural mechanism that an organization uses to motivate workers. Employees are the building blocks of an organization. Organizational success depends on the collective efforts of the staff. The employees will collectively contribute to organizational growth when they are motivated. (Susan, 2018) and Mbah, Ikechukwu & Chukwudi (2018)

Employee performance is critical to the success of any business. Achieving large goals requires a team of motivated team members working together. An effective Performance Management strategy can ensure your employees' activities and output are in line with your wider business objectives and can be critical to business success and employee productivity (Natural, 2022). There are different approaches to motivation that can be used within the organization such as fear, incentive and personal growth. Motivation level within the workplace has a direct impact on employee performance. The need to achieve organizational goals also underpins the need for employee motivation. Employee satisfaction and promoting a healthy human resource is identified as an important reason to motivate employees. Most organizations use incentives to foster physically and mentally healthy workforce by catering for their psychological needs. Offering incentives to human resources is vital in improving organizational productivity. Hence, the organization ought to leverage the plethora of incentive schemes and strategies as an option of boosting productivity (Aziri, 2019). A motivated employee is a business's most valuable asset. Research shows that a highly motivated employee has a higher level of employee performance while the opposite is true. To improve performance your human resource department must find creative ways to keep people motivated in the workplace. The present study sought to evaluate the motivational incentives and the performance of electricity services in South East, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the study

One of the critical facets of contemporary adaptation is employee motivation. When an employee sees his goals clearly defined, his performance challenges identified and career development solutions in place to help advance his career, the effect is to motivate the employee to achieve those goals. An employee performance appraisal can act as motivation for an employee to improve his productivity.

Motivation is considered as a predictor of job performance. Motivation and job performance are inextricably connected because every employee has to have some degree of motivation just to go to work in the first place. Many people believe that the most highly motivated employees are the employees who will reach the highest level of job performance. Consequently, most organizations often fail in the areas of motivating employees as a

result of lack of recognition/rewards and poor professional development in the areas of the organisational leaders and managers.

Opportunities for promotion can be a very positive motivational factor that can drive staff to work harder and motivate them to take the initiative in their work. For ensuring a good-quality performance from the employees of a business, there is nothing more crucial than performance evaluation. To ensure that the employees are performing up to expectations, employee performance evaluation is indispensable and as such related problems of motivations in the organization should be avoided in order to overcome meager output and poor quality products.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The main objectives of study were to evaluate motivational Incentives and the Performance of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria. The Specific Objectives:

- i. Examine the relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria?

1.5 Significant of the study

The study will help the management of electricity distribution companies and its entire workforce in understanding how motivational incentives can be used in motivating employees to make positive contribution towards performance of their jobs. In addition, it will also enable policy makers in the development of fitting incentive tools with appropriate rewards to satisfactorily motivate employees in other maximize acceptable standards of performance.

Furthermore, findings of the study will also benefit other organizations, manufacturing firms, government and private sectors in understanding incentives that could impact employee performance. The knowledge of the study will broaden the researcher's understanding on various motivational variables influencing employees' motivation.

Review of the related Literature

Conceptual review

2.1.1 Motivation

Motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behavior at a given time. Motivation is the process that initiates, guides, and maintains goal-oriented behaviors (Kendra, 2023). Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behavior. Motivation, forces acting either on or within a person to initiate behaviour. The word is derived from the Latin term *motivus* ("a moving cause"), which suggests the activating properties of the processes involved in psychological motivation. Motivational states can be expressed in various degrees of

strength, where the higher the degree, the more likely it is that the state exerts an influence on behavior (Souders, 2019). Finding ways to increase motivation is crucial because it allows us to change behavior, develop competencies, be creative, set goals, grow interests, make plans, develop talents, and boost engagement. Motivation is a vital resource that allows us to adapt, function productively, and maintain wellbeing in the face of a constantly changing stream of opportunities and threats. The concept of motivation can be extrinsic where motivations are harnessed from outside the person or intrinsic where motivation is derived from the person instead of external influence.

2.1.2 Incentives

Incentive is a powerful tool to influence certain desired behaviors or action. Incentive is a measure stimulating human effort, whereby employees are driven to put in their best. It is a tool that can be engaged by any employer of labour, whether public or private employer and regardless of the type of task involved (Oloke, Oni, Babalola & Ojelabi, 2017). “Incentive” may influence our conclusions regarding the relevance, effectiveness (and risks) of incentives. The term incentive is used and defined in one of two ways. First, the term incentive can be defined as “a promise of pay for some objective, pre-established level of performance,” which is often physical output (Newman, Gerhart & Milkovich, 2017). Incentive measures, such as salaries, secondary benefits, and intangible rewards, recognition or sanctions have traditionally been used to motivate employees to increase performance. Incentive systems reside within organizations, their structure, rules, human resource management, opportunities, internal benefits, rewards and sanctions, etc. Whether based on perception or reality, organizational incentive systems do have a significant influence on the performance of individuals and thus the organization overall.

2.1.3 Motivational incentives

Incentive systems and motivations are critical for capacity development as they enable individuals and organisations to perform their functions effectively, efficiently and sustainably. Motivation refers to the initiation, direction, intensity and persistence of behaviour. Incentives on the other hand are external measures that are designed and established to influence motivation and behaviour of individuals, groups or organizations. Motivation is what drives people to perform, grow, and achieve their goals in therapy, coaching, or organizational settings. While motivational incentives are external rewards by definition, they are not always tangible or monetary (Moore, 2021). An incentive is any valuable or desired item, object, action, or event that encourages an employee to perform more of the good work that the reward recognition acknowledges. Within a work environment, incentives can range from a financial incentive to nonmonetary recognition. Hansen, (2023) asserts that, the role of incentives in employee motivation becomes clear when the majority of workers are willing to quit if they don't feel appreciated by their company.

2.1.3.1 Recognition and rewards

Rewards and Recognition is a system where people are acknowledged for their performance in intrinsic or extrinsic ways. Recognition & Reward is present in a work environment where there is appropriate acknowledgement and appreciation of employees' efforts in a fair and timely manner. This includes appropriate and regular financial compensation, as well as employee or team celebrations, recognition of years served, and/or milestones reached (Darwinbox, 2023). Rewards and recognition are important tools that can be used to motivate employees and improve their performance. Rewards can include things such as bonuses, raises, or special privileges, while recognition can come in the form of words of appreciation or awards. Recognition reinforces what individuals want to see more of, thereby allowing them to see more good work and better performance.

Employee recognition and rewards should always be given genuinely – with no sneaky tricks to boost sales. Instead, recognition should be a regular thing. Both rewards and recognition are important when it comes to employee satisfaction and engagement (Hailey, 2023). They motivate in different ways. Reward programs work, if they are strongly linked to business objectives and the employees know what is expected of them in their jobs - employees need to see the connection between their own work and the overall goals of the company.

2.1.3.2 Professional development

Development is a process that creates growth, progress, positive change or the addition of physical, economic, environmental, social and demographic components. The purpose of development is a rise in the level and quality of life of the population, and the creation or expansion of local regional income and employment opportunities, without damaging the resources of the environment (SID, 2021). It is a process that ensures good quality of life to all the people in terms of happiness, harmony and satisfaction of essential needs. It is related to improvement, progress and aspirations of people. Professional development is gaining new skills through continuing education and career training after entering the workforce. It can include taking classes or workshops, attending professional or industry conferences, or earning a certificate to expand knowledge in individuals chosen field and contribute to success in the workplace. Professional development can also refer to staying up to date on new trends within your field and applying new practices to your current methods (Indeed, 2023). Professional development is important because it has the potential to open opportunities for career advancement, such as promotions. It can assist you in honing existing skills and in learning new ones.

2.1.4 Performance

Performance is a critical factor in organizational success, helping to also improve overall productivity, profitability, and employee morale. In the manufacturing firm, Performance is the firm's capability in achieving its objectives by utilizing resources in an effective as well as trustworthy means (Ahmad, Hadyait & Rashid, 2019). The term performance emerged in the mid-nineteenth century and was first used in defining the results to a sporting contest. Performance is also the success or fulfillment of organization at the end of program or projects as it is intended. In the twentieth century, the concept has evolved and developed a series of definitions that were meant to encompass the widest sense of what is perceived through performance (Ion and Criveanu, 2016). Performance can also be measured based on subjective information gathered from managers or other key informants, asking them to rate their company's overall performance such as their market share, profitability, innovation efforts, performance of human resource practices, and such other attributes.

2.1.4.1 Output

Output is a quantity of goods or services produced in a specific time period. For a business producing one good, output could simply be the number of units of that good produced in each time period, such as a month or a year. The business's output could also be approximated by the revenues from sales of the product, adjusted for price changes (inflation). Output refers to the total production of goods and services of a whole country over a given period – its gross domestic product. The term may refer to all the work, energy, goods, or services produced by an individual, company, factory or machine (Market Business News, 2022). For an industry, output is a measure of all the goods and services produced in a given time period by businesses in that industry and sold either to consumers or to businesses outside that industry.

2.1.4.2 Quality of products

Product quality or quality of products refers to how well a product satisfies customer needs, serves its purpose and meets industry standards. It involves considering several key factors which includes whether a product solves a problem, works efficiently or suits customers' purposes. For companies, product quality earns customer loyalty, helps establish brand recognition and manages costs. Customers often buy more from companies they know and trust, and businesses can reduce costs that result from product returns, defects and losses through product quality control. By ensuring product quality, you can help customers get to know your brand, encourage them to buy your products and increase your revenue (Indeed, 2023). Product Quality is the collection of all the features and characteristics of a product that contribute to its ability to meet the customer needs and requirements. It's the ability of the product to fulfil what the end user wants and perceives as value. For a product to be of good quality it should be reliable and perform all its functions smoothly (MBA, 2021). Product quality is single most important parameter for a product, brand or organization. The quality determines the customer experience and repeat business.

2.1.5 Electricity

Electricity is the flow of electrical power or charge. It is a secondary energy source which means that we get it from the conversion of other sources of energy, like coal, natural gas, oil, nuclear power and other natural sources, which are called primary sources. Electricity is a type of energy that consists of the movement of electrons between two points when there is a potential difference between them, making it possible to generate what is known as an electric current (Repsol, 2023). Electricity consumption, output, and price are cointegrated in the long run. In addition, it has been found that the relationship between electricity consumption and output is positive. In the long run, we find a unidirectional causality from manufacturing output to electricity consumption (Huseni & Lean, 2015).

2.1.6 Services

Service is any activity or benefit that one party can offer to another, which is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything. Services may be defined as intangible acts or performances whereby the service provider provides value to the customer. Services are intangible outcomes of human efforts (of deeds, processes, or performances) that can satisfy some human needs and thereby can command prices in exchange, except those which are illegal, immoral, or opposed to public policy (Ikhtiar, 2022). Service as, "an activity or series of activities rather than things which has some element of intangibility associated with it, which involves some interaction between the customer and the service provider, and does not result in a transfer of ownership. One reason for the poor quality of service levels across different service industries is that managers often tend to solve service marketing problems with tools and techniques that are essentially meant for tangible products. It happens because of inadequate understanding about the nature of services (Gaied, 2023).

2.1.7 Electricity services

Constant power supply is a major criterion for a nation's economic growth. The cost of service affects the affordability and sustainability of electrification programmes for rural communities. Electricity service providers must do everything possible to make their customers happy, satisfied and ensure they get the best value for their money in order to experience the numerical and financial growth their business desires as well as contribute to the nation's economic growth (Oladejo, 2010). Provision of constant, affordable and efficient electricity is very vital for economic growth, prosperity, national security as well as the rapid pace of industrialization in any nation.

Electric service means the supply of electricity, including generation, transmission, distribution and ancillary services (e.g. spinning and supplemental reserves) for ultimate consumption.

2.1.8 Conceptual Framework of the study

2.2 Theoretical Framework of the study

Herzberg’s Two- Factor Theory of Motivation Herzberg (1959) proposed a two-factor theory or the motivator-hygiene theory. According to Herzberg, there are some job factors that result in satisfaction while there are other job factors that prevent dissatisfaction. According to Herzberg, the opposite of “Satisfaction” is “No satisfaction” and the opposite of “Dissatisfaction” is “No Dissatisfaction”. Herzberg classified these job factors into two categories hygiene factors and motivational factors. Hygiene factors are those job factors which are essential for existence of motivation at workplace. These do not lead to positive satisfaction for long-term. But if these factors are absent / if these factors are non-existent at workplace, then they lead to dissatisfaction. In other words, hygiene factors are those factors which when adequate/reasonable in a job, pacify the employees and do not make them dissatisfied (Herzberg, 1959). These factors are extrinsic to work. Hygiene factors are also called as dissatisfiers or maintenance factors as they are required to avoid dissatisfaction. These factors describe the job environment/scenario. The hygiene factors symbolized the physiological needs which the individuals wanted and expected to be fulfilled. Motivational factors - According to Herzberg (1959), the hygiene factors could not be regarded as motivators. The motivational factors yield positive satisfaction and are inherent to work (Hertzberg, 1959). These factors motivate the employees for a superior performance. Motivational factors are called satisfiers and are involved in performing the job (ibid). The motivators symbolized the psychological needs that were perceived as an additional benefit.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 The relationship between recognition and rewards on the output

Lasisi, Adereti and Olamilokun (2021) conducted a study on a Challenges of Rewards System on Employees’ Performance in the Nigeria Civil Service: Empirical Evidence from the Lagos State Civil Service, Nigeria. Rewards play an important role in boosting employees’ performances in an organisation. The management of a rewards system has the potency of stimulating the interest of the employees and directing them towards accomplishing organisational goals. Despite the recognition and implementation of the rewards system in the civil

service, employees' performances have been highly criticized. Data were gathered from 275 respondents across the ministries in Civil Service through the use of questionnaire as well as the conduct of interview session. The findings revealed that leadership style, government policies, inability to pay, inadequate training, rewards strategies, bargaining power of trade union and strict organisational culture were challenges affecting effective management of rewards system. This study concluded that the administration of rewards system in the Nigerian public service has been poorly managed as it has been highly characterised by rewarding loyalty, nepotism, favouritism and godfatherism. This study therefore recommended a well-structured inclusive mechanism to encourage employee's participation in the service.

Alabi, Amusat and Asabi (2022) conducted a study on the Effect of Reward System on the Performance of Employees: A Study of Selected Commercial Banks in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. The study investigated the effect of reward system on the performance of employees in selected commercial banks in Osogbo metropolis, Osun State, Nigeria. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 71 respondents out of 128 permanent staff through random sampling method. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected in order to examine the effect of independent variable, reward system dimensions (salary, recognition and bonus), on dependent variable (employees' performance). The result showed that the dimensions of reward system have significant effect on employees' performance. Based on this, it is concluded that the predictor variables namely (salary (0.372); recognition (0.251); bonus (0.328)) are jointly 78.0 percent variance of employees' performance.

Oduayo, (2022) conducted a study on the Effect of Organizational Reward System on Employee Performance in Selected Hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. The study investigates effect of organisational reward system on employee performance in selected hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. The objective was to establish effect of organisational reward system (Recognition, Employee Development, and Benefits) on employee performance (contextual performance, counterproductive behaviour, and adaptive behaviour) in selected hotels in Lagos Metropolis using a survey research design. Two hotels were sampled and used for the study. A total population of 315 employees were investigated with a sample size of 255. In this research, a simple random sampling technique was adopted, and only 204 copies (or 80 percent) of the questionnaire were properly completed and recovered. To determine the link between the variables, the data was examined using the bivariate regression analysis. The investigation revealed that recognition had significant effect on contextual performance in selected hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.592$, $t = 12.353$, $p < 0.05$). The finding also revealed that employees' development has a negative and significant effect on counterproductive behaviour in selected hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria ($\beta = -0.244$, $t = 6.441$, $p < 0.05$). Also, it was discovered that benefits had significant effect on adaptive performance in selected hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.399$, $t = 9.339$, $p < 0.05$). As a result, it was concluded that organisational reward system affected employee performance in selected hotels in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria.

Shahzad, Khan, Iqbal, Omer and Shabbir (2023) carried out a study on the Effects of Motivational and Behavioral Factors on Job Productivity: An Empirical Investigation from Academic Librarians in Pakistan. The major objective of the current study was to find out the impact of motivational factors on the job outcomes of librarians working in HEC-recognized university libraries in Pakistan. A survey research method followed by predictive correlational design was applied to test the constructed hypotheses in this study. The population of the study was library professionals working in the university libraries of Lahore, Pakistan. There were 13 public sector

universities and 21 private sector universities. The census sampling technique was used to collect data from the respondents of the 34 universities. Data were collected with the help of a questionnaire. Out of 225 respondents, 189 completed questionnaires were received. Hence, the response rate was 84%. The gathered data were analyzed through SPSS software. Descriptive and inferential statistical tests were applied to find out the impact of motivational and behavioral factors on the job outcomes of information professionals. The findings of the study showed that different types of motivation influenced information professionals to carry out innovative and value-added services in the workplace. Rewards, a sense of honor, an amicable work environment, and autonomy were the key categories of motivation that encouraged information professionals to undertake efficient job performance.

Stanfast and Stanfast (2023) carried out a study on the Intrinsic Reward Systems and Employees' Commitment of Deposit Money Banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. This study examined the relationship between intrinsic reward systems and employees' commitment of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. Cross-sectional survey design was used for the study. The study had a population of 315 respondents' that cut across 10 selected deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. The study sample was 176 employees of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt derived from the use of systematic sampling technique. The data collected was subjected to analysis using Partial Least Squares (PLS) – Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with the aid of Smart PLS 3.3.3. The result of the study showed a positive and significant relationship between intrinsic rewards and the measures of employees' commitment (affective, continuance and normative commitment). The study concluded that rewards system is a driver of employees' commitment in the Nigerian banking sector as confirmed by the result of the study.

2.3.2 The relationship between professional development and the quality of products

Abdulrahman, Abdulraheem and Ismaila (2017) conducted a study on the Impact of Electricity Service Quality on the Performance of Manufacturing SMEs in Nigeria. The objective of this paper is to determine the impact of electricity service quality on both financial and non-financial performance of manufacturing Small and Medium Enterprises SMEs in Nigeria. Design/Methodology/Approach: Survey questionnaire was used to collect data from 201 Managers, Chief executive officers and owner managers of SMEs that are members of Manufacturers Association of Nigeria MAN. Simple regression analysis was done with the use of SPSS version 22.0. Findings: The results indicate that quality of electricity tends to account for more than 50% of the variances in the financial and non-financial performance of manufacturing SMEs in Nigeria. Implications/Originality/Value: This paper contributes to the existing literature on the empirical investigation into the use of service quality as a measure of electricity service and also emphasizes the importance of electricity to the performance of manufacturing SMEs in the developing countries. It recommends that future research may consider collecting longitudinal data to eliminate bias related to time. Key words: Electricity service quality, Manufacturing performance, SMEs, Nigeria Ibrahim, Shuaibu and Ibrahim (2017) conducted a study on the Relationship Between Electricity Consumption, Manufacturing Output and Financial Development: A New Evidence from Nigeria. Article History Electricity is regarded as sine quo non for any meaningful social, economic and modern scientific advancement of any country in the world. It is regarded as a force and engine room of the industrial sector. However, in Nigeria, instability in power supply is negatively affecting manufacturing efficiency. Time series data for 1981 until 2015 was used to examine the symmetric relationship between the electric consumption, manufacturing output and financial development in Nigeria. The result indicates the co-movement in the variable over long time horizon, meaning that any inefficiency in electricity supply would impeded industrial output. Moreover, the Granger causality test

based on vector error correction framework shows the presence of causality between power utilization of manufacturing firms and economic growth without feedback. In this sense it can be stress that stable electricity consumption is important factor for Nigeria's manufacturing sector. The result of variance decomposition further indicates that the variation in the industrial output responds more to shocks in the electricity supply than its own shock. This finding suggests that energy is the engine of manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Okibe and Mokuye (2018) carried out a study on an Appraisal of Power Sector Reforms and Delivery of Electric Services in Nigeria. The performance of the power sector in Nigeria since its reform as provided for in the Electric Power Sector Reform Act (EPSR Act, 2005) constitutes source of concern amongst government policymakers, stakeholders in the power industry and the public. Several efforts to ascertain how well the sector delivers electricity effectively to its users since the period seem to provide vague database. This study assessed the performance of the power sector before the 2005 reform and thereafter, to ascertain the implication within the electricity value chain, and how it affects the living standards of the people. As a descriptive study, it sourced information from secondary data, used content analysis method for discussion of the thematic issues and anchored the study on elite theory, primarily to demonstrate how a tiny segment of the society makes policies that target their mutual interests and benefits, other than the masses. The findings show, firstly, that government's interference and excessive control contributes to the failures in the reform and privatization of the power sector. Secondly, members of the public pay exorbitant cost to use electricity facility even when it is scarcely available. Thirdly, the present predicaments of the power sector are not different from what it was before government embarked on the sector's privatization. It recommends repositioning the privatized power sector operations for greater efficiency in service delivery.

Mohammed (2020) conducted a study on Incentives and employees of Polytechnics in the Northeast Nigeria: The Nexus. The study is aimed at examining the relationship between incentives and employees within the Polytechnics in Northeast Nigeria. The research was quantitative and explanatory, where a cross-sectional survey of 722 Academic and senior non-Academic staff of 10 Polytechnics in Northeast Nigeria was carried out using random sampling techniques. However, data were collected using a structured questionnaire, distributed with the aid of field assistants; the data were analyzed via IBM SPSS software version 2.0. The analyses of the variables Incentive, Employees (performance, Motivation, Job satisfaction) show a positive and significant relationship between incentive and job performance, motivation and job satisfaction.

Ede, and Mbah, (2020), conducted a study on the evaluation of the relationship between organizational compensation and employee output in five selected manufacturing firms in south-east, Nigeria. The population for the study was five thousand, and eleven employees (5,011). The study sample size was eight hundred and ninety-five (895) respondents. Questionnaire which was validated by experts was the instrument used for data collection. Some of the major findings is that there is a positive relationship between access to training and employee product quality in the five selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria ($r = .780$; $p = .000 > 0.05$, $n=895$); there is a positive relationship between organizational compensation and employees output in the five selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria ($r = .840$; $p = .000 > 0.05$, $n=895$). The study concluded that that if employees are well compensated and well trained, it will encourage more productivity and overall output. Consequent upon the findings, some recommendations were made; It is recommended that employees should be given access to continual training of all types just to keep up, firms should invest resources in training and coaching employees, which will, in turn, give their employees a sense of ethical obligation to respond with

increased effort, and a desire to stay with the organization to 'repay the debt, Finally, firms should strategically structure their compensation plan accordingly. This can be done informally by asking employees with other companies that you interview about their compensation plan, or more objectively by hiring an outside consulting firm to benchmark their plan against others and advise you on how to adjust it.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The area of the study comprised staff of Electricity Services in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 470 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 211, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 194 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 92 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.81 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool.

4.0 Data Presentation and Analyses

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 The relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 4.1.1.1: Responses on the relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decisio
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		n
1	There is proper acknowledgement and appreciation of staff's effort in a fair and timely manner in the organisation.	355	148	48	58	41	650	3.35	1.594	Agree
		71	37	16	29	41	194			
		36.6	19.1	8.2	14.	21.	100%			
					9	1				
2	The monthly newsletter with staff success stories makes the workers to work hard.	240	148	75	36	66	565	2.91	1.625	Agree
		48	37	25	18	66	194			
		24.4	19.1	12.9	9.3	34.	100%			
						0				
3	Distinguished staff are provided with learning and development opportunities.	335	164	78	40	40	657	3.39	1.544	Agree
		67	41	26	20	40	194			
		34.5	21.1	13.4	10.	20.	100%			
					3	6				
4	Enabling gratification leads to higher productivity.	405	140	21	80	31	677	3.49	1.571	Agree
		81	35	7	40	31	194			
		41.8	18.0	3.6	20.	16.	100%			
					6	0				

5	Magnifying recognition drive staff engagement in the electricity services.	375 75 38.7	140 35 18.0	48 16 8.2	40 20 10.	48 48 24.	651 194 100%	3.36	1.645	Agree
					3	7				

Total Grand mean and standard deviation

**3.3 1.595
8**

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1.1, 108 respondents out of 194 representing 55.7 percent agreed that there is proper acknowledgement and appreciation of staff’s effort in a fair and timely manner in the organization with mean score 3.35 and standard deviation of 1.594. The monthly newsletter with staff success stories makes the workers to work hard 85 respondents representing 43.5 percent agreed with mean score of 2.91 and standard deviation of 1.625. Distinguished staff are provided with learning and development opportunities 108 respondents representing 55.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.39 and standard deviation of 1.544. Enabling gratification leads to higher productivity 116 respondents representing 59.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.49 and 1.571. Magnifying recognition drive staff engagement in the electricity services 110 respondents representing 56.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.36 and standard deviation 1.645.

4.2.1 The relationship between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 4.2.1.1: Responses on the relationship between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decisio
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		n
1	Training help provide the customer’s needs in the electricity services.	395 79 40.7	204 51 26.3	21 7 3.6	84 42 21.	15 15 7.7	719 194 100%	3.71	1.389	Agree
					6					
2	Labour availability as a result of quality skills.	300 60 30.9	204 51 26.3	3 1 .5	72 36 18.	46 46 23.	625 194 100%	3.22	1.612	Agree
					6	7				
3	The effective distribution of electricity services was due skilled manpower.	340 68 35.1	212 53 27.3	18 6 3.1	80 40 20.	27 27 13.	677 194 100%	3.49	1.487	Agree
					6	9				
4	Technology and materials for production creation was based on expertise.	320 64 33.0	164 41 21.1	69 23 11.9	8 4 2.1	62 62 32.	623 194 100%	3.21	1.673	Agree
						0				

5	The level of experience and knowledge lead to meet industry standards.	405 81 41.4	120 30 15.5	42 14 7.2	82 41 21.	41 41 14.	690 264 100%	2.61	1.545	Agree
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Total Grand mean and standard deviation	3.24	1.541
	8	2

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.2.1, 130 respondents out of 194 representing 67.0 percent agreed that Training help provide the customer’s needs in the electricity services with mean score 3.71 and standard deviation of 1.389. Labour availability as a result of quality skills 111 respondents representing 57.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.22 and standard deviation of 1.612. The effective distribution of electricity services was due skilled manpower 212 respondents representing 62.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.49 and standard deviation of 1.487. Technology and materials for production creation was based on expertise 105 respondents representing 54.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.21 and 1.673. The level of experience and knowledge lead to meet industry standards 111 respondents representing 56.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 2.61 and standard deviation 1.545.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypotheses One: There is no positive relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

Correlations

	There is proper acknowledgement and appreciation of staff's effort in fair and timely manner in the organisation.	The monthly newsletters with staff success stories and makes the workers to work hard.	Distinguished staff are provided with learning and development opportunities.	Enabling gratification leads to higher productivity.	Magnifying recognition drive staff engagement in the electricity services.
There is proper acknowledgement and appreciation	Pearson Correlation	.622**	.633**	.550**	.559**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000

of staff's effort in a fair and timely manner in the organisation.	N	194	194	194	194	194
The monthly newsletter with staff success stories makes workers to work hard.	Pearson Correlation	.622**	1	.532**	.413**	.392**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
Distinguished staff provided with learning and development opportunities.	N	194	194	194	194	194
	Pearson Correlation	.633**	.532**	1	.547**	.749**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
Enabling gratification on leads to higher productivity.	N	194	194	194	194	194
	Pearson Correlation	.550**	.413**	.547**	1	.620**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
Magnifying recognition drive staff engagement in the electricity services.	N	194	194	194	194	194
	Pearson Correlation	.559**	.392**	.749**	.620**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on **recognition and rewards on the output** showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.150 < .860$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that **there was positive significant relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria**, ($r = .392 < .794$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .392 < .794$, $p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .392 < .794$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .392 < .794, p < .05$).

4.3.2 Hypotheses Two: There is no positive linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

Correlations

	Trainin g help provide the custom er's needs in the electrici ty services	Labour availab ility as a result of quality skills.	The effectiv e distrib ution of electrici ty services was due to skilled manpow er.	Technol ogy and materials for producti on creation was based on expertise s.	The level of experien ce and knowled ge lead to meet industry standard skills.	
Training help provide the customer's needs in the electricity services.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2- tailed) N	1 .700** .000 194	.700** .000 194	.695** .000 194	.553** .000 194	.560** .000 194
Labour availability as a result of quality skills.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2- tailed) N	.700** .000 194	1 .709** .000 194	.709** .000 194	.538** .000 194	.549** .000 194
The effective distribution of electricity services due skilled manpower.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2- tailed) N	.695** .000 194	.709** .000 194	1 .548** .000 194	.548** .000 194	.529** .000 194

Technology and materials for production based on expertise.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.553**	.538**	.548**	1	.425**
	N	194	194	194	194	194
The level of experience and knowledge lead to meet industry standards.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.560**	.549**	.529**	.425**	1
	N	194	194	194	194	194

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on professional development and the quality showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.425 < .700$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .425 < .700$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .425 < .700, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .425 < .700$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .425 < .700, p < .05$).

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

From the computed result of Hypothesis one ($r = .392 < .794$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, Therefore, we concluded that there was positive relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .392 < .794, p < .05$). In literature review, it was supported by Lasisi, Adereti and Olamilokun (2021) conducted a study on a Challenges of Rewards System on Employees' Performance in the Nigeria Civil Service: Empirical Evidence from the Lagos State Civil Service, Nigeria. The study concluded that the administration of rewards system in the Nigerian public service has been poorly managed as it has been highly characterised by rewarding loyalty, nepotism, favouritism and godfatherism. This study therefore recommended a well-structured inclusive mechanism to encourage employee's participation in the service. Alabi, Amusat and Asabi (2022) conducted a study on the Effect of Reward System on the Performance of Employees: A Study of Selected Commercial Banks in Osogbo Metropolis, Osun State,

Nigeria. The result showed that the dimensions of reward system have significant effect on employees' performance. Based on this, it is concluded that the predictor variables namely (salary (0.372); recognition (0.251); bonus (0.328)) are jointly 78.0 percent variance of employees' performance. Shahzad, Khan, Iqbal, Omer and Shabbir (2023) carried out a study on the Effects of Motivational and Behavioral Factors on Job Productivity: An Empirical Investigation from Academic Librarians in Pakistan. The findings of the study showed that different types of motivation influenced information professionals to carry out innovative and value-added services in the workplace. Rewards, a sense of honor, an amicable work environment, and autonomy were the key categories of motivation that encouraged information professionals to undertake efficient job performance.

4.4.2 Linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria

From the computed result of Hypothesis two ($r = .425 < .700$) was greater than the table value of .000, Therefore, we concluded that **there was positive linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria** as reported in the probability value of ($r = .425 < .700, p < .05$). In literature review, it was supported by Abdulrahman, Abdulraheem and Ismaila (2017) conducted a study on the Impact of Electricity Service Quality on the Performance of Manufacturing SMEs in Nigeria. The results indicated that quality of electricity tends to account for more than 50% of the variances in the financial and non-financial performance of manufacturing SMEs in Nigeria. Ibrahim, Shuaibu and Ibrahim (2017) conducted a study on the Relationship Between Electricity Consumption, Manufacturing Output and Financial Development: A New Evidence from Nigeria. The result indicates the co-movement in the variable over long time horizon, meaning that any inefficiency in electricity supply would impede industrial output. Moreover, the Granger causality test based on vector error correction framework shows the presence of causality between power utilization of manufacturing firms and economic growth without feedback. In this sense it can be stress that stable electricity consumption is important factor for Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

5.1 Summary of findings

Based on the result, the following findings were made:

- i. There was positive relationship between recognition and rewards on the output of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria, ($r = .392 < .794, p < .05$).
- ii. There was positive linkage between professional development and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria, ($r = .425 < .700$).

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that recognition and rewards, professional development had positive significant relationship with the output and the quality of products of Electricity Services in Enugu State, Nigeria. Offering incentives to human resources is vital in improving organizational productivity. Hence, the organization ought to leverage the plethora of incentive schemes and strategies as an option of boosting productivity. A motivated employee is a business's most valuable asset. Research shows that a highly motivated employee has a higher level of employee performance while the opposite is true.

5.3 Recommendations

1. The management should endeavour to Recognise hard work and reward the employees to motivate the staff, which will boost teamwork and productivity. It will improve the workplace culture and creating a supportive work environment.

2. For an effective success there is need for Professional development to help booster employees' confidence in their work.

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